

RESIN PLASTICS.*

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The choice of plastics as a subject for this address has been influenced by two main reasons : firstly, the ever-increasing share which plastic products are taking in the arts and industries generally during the last quarter of a century, and secondly, the absence of any plastics industry in India based on her own raw materials, natural or synthetic. Whilst the production of synthetic plastic materials is dependent on an all-round industrial development, the existence of the natural resin in shellac in the country raises the question whether this unique raw product could not be the basis of a commercially feasible plastic industry *i.e.*, in reasonable competition with synthetics. It would appear from statistical considerations that the demand for shellac has gone on continually increasing, and in fact, from an export figure of 308,937 cwt. in 1920-21, it stands at 760,399 cwt. in 1939-40 in spite of the tremendous output of various synthetic resins in the countries importing shellac. This alone is proof positive of the superiority of this natural product over many of the synthetics, at least in certain industrial uses. About 300,000 maunds (11,000 tons) of shellac are consumed by the gramophone record making industry, which the synthetic resin has scarcely been able to penetrate into. The largest application of synthetics is in the moulding of household articles, specially, electro-technical, and how far shellac as such or modified can be substituted would be discussed later. When an industry is faced with the disposal and utilisation of its by-products, a sort of inevitable competition between such products and similar natural or agricultural products makes its appearance, and the fate of the natural product is determined by its performance efficiency and price as compared with its synthetic rival. Vested interest actuates the producers of both the synthetic and the natural product, and the consumer, who has ultimately to face the music, would naturally welcome the presence of both commodities in the market for his choice. Improvements by research for ultimate processing of both classes of materials is, therefore, an important feature in the economic development of industries dependent on them. There is, however, another aspect of the problem—the combination of the natural with the synthetic product to suit local conditions or

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secure better performance, which has not attracted the attention it deserves. Whilst a review of the synthetic resin industry with special reference to its development in India will be at first attempted, later, specific cases of quasi-synthetic plastic materials will be discussed and their value in national economy clearly indicated. It is hoped that the attention of the State will be directed to an enquiry whether a plastics industry based on India's natural products cannot be developed, and, if so, what steps it should take to bring such an industry into being.

Plastic resins may be classified into two groups—thermoplastic and thermo-hardening.

A. Thermoplastic resins :—Shellac, glycol polybasic acid resins, vinyl resins, polystyrene, polyindene, novolacks, protein resins, etc.

B. Thermo-hardening resins :—Phenol-aldehyde resins, urea-aldehyde resins, heat convertible alkyds, etc.

A consideration of the composition of synthetic resins would reveal that a few raw materials, which are by-products of some principal industries, are chemically and physically treated to produce high molecular or polymeric compounds with adequate plasticity which either remains intact during moulding or is changed thereby. The chart on p. 49 illustrates the sources of raw materials.

The availability of such starting materials is the condition precedent for the development of a synthetic resin plastic industry in this country. Looking at the chart it cannot be said that raw materials for synthetic resins are as yet available at such prices and in requisite quantities that can warrant the laying down of the foundation of this industry. There appears, therefore, to be a decided advantage, for the time being at any rate, in favour of natural or quasi-natural plastics. Taking the case of bakelite, the most important of the synthetic resins, the two essential materials, phenol and formaldehyde are as yet not available, particularly the latter, the manufacture of which is still only a project. As to phenol, no doubt a quantity of it could be had as a by-product of the coking industry, but its price is far too high in the present state of the tar-distillation industry to allow of its being used in plastics production. As for formaldehyde, there is at present methyl alcohol available at the Mysore Iron Works, Bhadravati, at a cost of Rs. 3/8/- per gallon, but synthetic methanol costs only 1rd. This is by

THE DERIVATION OF CERTAIN SYNTHETIC RESINS

From U. S. Tariff Commission Report No. 131 "Synthetic Resins" with Comarone and Indene added.

way of the economics of bakelite manufacture in India.* Considering however, that the availability of these two raw materials, phenol and formaldehyde, is probable in the near future, the investigation of problems relating to the technical manufacture of bakelite should engage the attention of research chemists. The theory of bakelite formation is tolerably well-understood by now, but investigation on the plastic nature to effect further improvement is far from complete. Then again, a whole range of experiments with different phenols and bi-phenols might lead to still superior products, whilst the problem of fillers, especially, wood flour from Indian wood, has not yet been touched.

The next important synthetic resin is that derived from the condensation of urea with formaldehyde. Here again, the manufacture of urea by the cheapest possible process has to be brought into existence in this country before this type of resin could be manufactured economically. Many are the methods suggested for the production of this important chemical, but its synthesis from carbon dioxide and ammonia and production from calcium cyanamide are the two practicable processes so far developed for its manufacture. These methods have been tested on more than a laboratory scale at the Indian Lac Research Institute, as this chemical and a few allied ones (*vide infra*) have been found to be excellent accelerators in the manufacture of moulding powders from shellac and modified shellac. A semi-large scale plant for and method of operation of each of the processes are described in 'Practical Applications of Recent Lac Research' published by the Indian Lac Research Institute.

PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE.

As early as 1872, Baeyer studied the reaction products of benzaldehyde with pyrogallol acid and resorcinol, acetaldehyde or chloral with resorcinol, methylene acetate with phenol, etc. He established the fact that aldehydes and phenols, under suitable conditions, yield resinous products. Smith in 1900 and many others before him had noticed the reaction, and in fact, Trillat in 1896 had described the condensation of phenol and aldehydes in the presence of mineral acids and exhibited several artificial resins in the Paris Exhibition of 1900. The merit of Baekeland lay, however, in the discovery that under pressure and heat such resins were converted into

* Several cheap sources of formaldehyde are indicated in recent patent literature. These are ethylene, methane, coal-gas, etc. In the absence of cheap synthetic methyl alcohol, experiments on the conversion of low-temperature carbonisation gas and ethyl alcohol into formaldehyde are being attempted at the Indian Lac Research Institute with promising results. The catalytic oxidation is conducted under ordinary atmospheric pressure, and as such there are less plant constructional difficulties.

insoluble and infusible substances. The theoretical basis of every such reaction is well understood until the stage at which a thick syrupy or pasty mass is produced. Opinions differ as to the interpretation of the further course of resinification by polymerisation and condensation. Several hypotheses based on experimental evidence, analogies and theoretical considerations have been advanced. Phenol and formaldehyde react resulting in either a diphenyl ether (I) and a methylene diphenol (II), by condensation, in an acid medium, or an aldol formation (III), by addition, in an alkaline medium :—

The formation of the diphenyl ether (m.p. 18°), methylene diphenol (m.p. 160·2°) and hydroxybenzyl alcohol (m.p. 87°) has been demonstrated. By the application of heat, the alkali-catalysed products polymerise and Baekland considers that a ring compound is formed, whereas Herzog and Krcidl believe that the molecule exists as a lattice structure. The acid-catalysed resins are permanently soluble and fusible and are not much in use.

Equimolecular proportions of phenol and formaldehyde (94 g. of phenol + 75 g. of formalin) with 1% by weight of concentrated ammonia are digested at 80°–90° and cooled, when the mass separates into an aqueous upper layer and a pale straw-coloured liquid. The water and traces of uncombined phenol are removed by vacuum distillation at 65°–70° and the resin is discharged into shallow trays and cooled quickly. An important variation in this process is to condense phenol with part of the formaldehyde in the presence of alkali or acid and after dehydration, to add hexamethylenetetramine. Other aldehydes like furfural, and phenols like cresols and resorcinol, when cheap and abundant, are used for making similar resins.

It may be mentioned in this connection that almost all the synthetic resins are formed by condensation reactions in which generally water is eliminated and sometimes halogen hydrides, hydrogen sulphide, ammonia or hydrogen are liberated. If the resulting products contain residual unsaturation points or double bonds, they are non-hardening. Resins, as mentioned above, may be divided into two types : permanently fusible resins or thermoplastic, and those which are polymerised to an infusible state by heat and pressure or thermo-hardening resins. With this criterion of resin formation, it can be imagined what an endless variety of resins is

possible and chemists all over the world have vigorously pursued this line of investigation for the last 28 years *i.e.* ever since Dr. Baekeland established the commercial success of phenolic synthetic plastics. Every variation of the reactants, catalysts, and various modifying agents are being examined. But among all the known synthetic resins for plastics, although a few might be preferred to phenolics for special applications, none has approached the great commercial success attained by the latter. Phenol-formaldehyde resins are used for many other industries besides plastics in which latter field they are either used as castings in the shape of rods, tubes or imitation jewellery or as composite mouldings when mixed with fillers, dyes or pigment. The moulded articles are used in electrical insulations, household appliances, scientific apparatus, machinery, etc.

UREA-FORMALDEHYDE RESINS.

Although phenol-formaldehyde resins enjoyed a large measure of popularity within the first decade of their commercial development, the aesthetic tastes of the public demanded moulded materials in lighter shades of colour than the black, brown and dark green of the phenolics. Urea-formaldehyde resin moulded articles, otherwise called amino-plastics, were the answer to this need. Amino-plastics are only second to phenolic plastics and moulded articles in all pastel shades from glass-like transparency through varying degrees of translucency to opacity are available.

It was known as early as 1884 that the reaction between urea and formaldehyde results in resin-like materials, but it was in 1896 that the definite nature of the reaction under *neutral*, *acidic* and *alkaline* conditions was investigated and understood. The commercial application of such resins for moulded articles started as recently as 1921, and Pollak established the conditions necessary for producing mouldable substances between 1920 and 1927.

The products formed by the reaction of urea with formaldehyde vary according to the proportion of the two and the p_H of the medium. Their composition and properties are also different. In acid solution, the following reactions take place :—

The end-products occur as polymers, although their chemical compositions are as indicated by their monomeric formulae. $(C_2H_4N_2O)_x$ is an amorphous powder, slightly soluble in water and splits up again into the original constituents by the action of mineral acids. $(C_6H_{10}N_4O_3)_x$ is obtained as a granular precipitate when the amount of formaldehyde used is 1.5 to 2 molecules per molecule of urea. Higher proportions of formaldehyde result in $(C_8H_{12}N_4O_4)_x$ in smaller yields.

When formaldehyde is added to a solution of urea and barium hydroxide in water at 0° , (*i.e.* in alkaline solution) monomethylol urea is formed.

The product is easily soluble in water and in methyl alcohol but insoluble in ether. It crystallises from alcohol in prisms with a melting point of 111° . On the other hand, when urea is added to barium hydroxide in formaldehyde solution at 25° , dimethylol urea is obtained, which is soluble in warm ethyl or methyl alcohol. It melts at 126° to a liquid which again solidifies at 133° with the liberation of water and formaldehyde, which, on heating further, decomposes without melting at 260° .

In neutral solutions, the following three reactions have been found to take place according as one, two, or more molecular proportions of formaldehyde are reacted with urea.

Urea-formaldehyde resins find applications in the field of adhesives, glass substitutes and moulded wares. According to the nature of application, different methods of producing the resins are adopted, and numerous patents have been taken out claiming diverse properties. A typical method of producing glass-like masses is as follows:—

One molecule of urea and 2 molecules of formaldehyde are heated under reflux in the presence of hexamethylenetetramine until a clear, homogeneous liquid is produced. At this stage, a small quantity of sodium acetate is added to the liquid to prevent quick gelation and then most of the water is removed by vacuum distillation. Urea is again added to neutralise the acid reaction of the product and also to combine with the unreacted formaldehyde. Water is then distilled off and the product is hardened

This compound is considered to be the monomer of the polymerisation product which can be formed by the interaction of the remaining carboxyl groups with the β -hydroxy groups of the intermediate compound. To illustrate, 31 parts of glycerine and 74 parts of phthalic anhydride are heated together at 180°-200° until a drop of the product, when cooled, has a melting point of 90°. From local considerations, it would appear that a pound of glyptal may be produced at as low as 12 as. which is considerably higher than the price of most natural resins. Alkyd resins possess good adhesive, electrical, mechanical and thermal properties but their thermosetting is very slow. When polymerised, the resin is resistant to water and chemicals. A long range of products may be obtained by modifications effected by reacting with other organic acids, drying and non-drying oils, natural resins, etc. Recently, at the Indian Lac Research Institute, glycerol has been replaced by aleuritic acid, (1-hydroxy-7:8-dihydroxypalmitic acid) derived from the hydrolysis of shellac, and a solid resin functioning as a good plasticiser has been isolated. The use of lactic acid as a substitute for glycerol in the formation of alkyd resins has also been reported by Stearn, Makower and Groggins (*Ind. Eng. Chem.* 1940, 32, 1335), and the cheap production of the acid by fermentation would constitute a first step towards commercialising this interesting resin.

ETHENOID RESINS.

(i) *Acrylic acid Resins.* Of late, glass-clear resins, prepared from polymerised acrylic acid or its esters, have largely been used for automobile parts, air-craft industry, watch crystals, prisms and lenses. The starting materials for the manufacture of these resins are ethyl alcohol and carbon dioxide which may be available at a cheap cost in this country. With the large quantity of molasses as a by-product of the sugar industry, both ethyl alcohol and carbon dioxide could be obtained in abundant quantities. A mixture of ethyl alcohol and carbon dioxide is passed over a dehydrating catalyst to first convert alcohol into ethylene. This mixture is then led into a chamber maintained at 200-300° and reacted in presence of a catalyst (*e.g.* sulphur dioxide, sodium acid phosphate) to form acrylic acid $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOH}$. Polymerised acrylic acid is itself resinous, but generally methyl or ethyl esters are used. Polymerised acrylic acid and its esters are glass-like thermoplastic resins which are sold in the form of sheets or powder and are eminently fitted for moulding curved or intricate glass-clear articles. The resin is sold under the name

of Leucon, Perspex or Diakon in England and as Plexiglass, Plexigum and Acryloid in Germany and America.

(ii) *Vinyl and Styrol Resins.* When acetylene is conducted rapidly through glacial acetic acid in the presence of mercuric sulphate at 70°, vinylacetic acid ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$) is obtained which is then polymerised into straight chain polyvinyl acetate by heat. Polyvinyl acetate polymerises to hard infusible masses on heating at 100°. Polymers of vinyl halides are prepared from acetylene and these are less soluble and stable than the esters. It is only the co-polymer of the halide and the ester that finds a large application in industries for the manufacture of gramophone records, dentures, brush handles, tumblers, glass substitutes, etc.

Styrene or vinylbenzene ($\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) is a colourless liquid, (b.p. 145°), prepared from ethylbenzene by pyrogenic dehydrogenation or by chlorinating and removing hydrochloric acid. It is polymerised into several grades of resins by carrying out the operation at low temperatures (100°) or high temperatures (180°) or in the presence of catalysts like oxygen and peroxides, acids, halides, alkalis. The resins produced are all glass-clear and have melting points ranging from 100° to 180°. Polystyrene resins are perfectly thermoplastic and are ideal for electrical insulations, and for injection moulding.

COUMARONE AND INDENE RESINS.

Coumarone resins are prepared from coal-tar fractions boiling at 150°-200°. On redistillation, a fraction is obtained containing about 30% of polymerisable compounds, these compounds consisting chiefly of coumarone (I), the isomeric methyl coumarones, indene (II) and possibly isomeric methylindenes. Sulphuric acid is used as the polymerising

catalyst, an appropriate amount of which is run into the liquid with stirring. The reaction temperature favours the production of dark coloured resins. When viscosity determination shows that polymerisation has reached its maximum, the liquor is neutralised, washed, tar decanted off, and the

residual liquor distilled in vacuum to give yellowish, permanently fusible resins. Polymerisation is believed to be of the following nature :—

Coumarone resins are yellowish in colour and not particularly light-stable. They are oil-soluble and used largely for certain types of alkali-resistant coating compositions, printing inks and in rubber compounding. These resins have found only a limited application in the plastics industry because, although they are cheap, resistant to moisture, and excellent as electrical insulating materials, they are too brittle and possess a low tensile strength.

KETONE RESINS.

The process for the production of ketone resins consists in condensing acetone with formaldehyde in the presence of a mild alkaline catalyst to give a mono methylol derivative, a keto-alcohol, which is treated with one of the common dehydrating agents to give a methylene derivative—an unsaturated ketone—which can be polymerised by heat and light, to give a thermoplastic resin. It was found, however, that by using acetone, the two preliminary stages were apt to get out of control. Hence the homologue, methylethyl ketone is now used in preference to acetone, as the reactions are more readily controlled. The reactions involved with methyl ethyl ketone are :

The resin is tough, colourless, transparent, machinable, thermoplastic and acetone-soluble.

CASEIN PLASTICS.

Casein, obtained by the treatment of skimmed milk with rennet, is the raw material for casein plastics manufacture. This casein, conforming to certain standards, particularly with regard to ash, fat and sugar content, is left with about 30% of its weight of water in the cold, until the casein particles are completely hydrated to casein gel. Colouring matters are generally added during this mixing stage. The gel is homogenised and moulded to a composite mass by passing through an extruding machine which consists essentially of a heated barrel in which operates an Archimedean screw which forces the material through screens and then through a heated nozzle at the end of the barrel. By this means rods of considerable length might be extruded, the size and shape of the rod being controlled by the nozzle. The rods are then soaked in dilute formaldehyde solution (about 5% CH_2O) until the formaldehyde has penetrated right through the material, the time of soaking obviously depending upon the thickness of the rods. This formalising process hardens the casein material rendering it tougher and less susceptible to moisture. After formalising, the rods are dried, straightened, tapped to constant diameter and are mop polished or given a high gloss by treatment with sodium hypochlorite solution. The rods can be converted into sheet forms by hot pressing before hardening with formaldehyde. By far the largest use of casein plastics is for buttons and buckles for womens' clothes. Other uses of casein material are for knitting pins, combs, etc.

The total world production of casein is estimated at 70,000 tons a year, out of which about 10,000 tons may be used in the field of plastics.

The general drawback met with in casein plastics is the time required for formalising casein in order to make it water-resistant. The presence of certain high paraffinic acids has a tendency to impart water-proofness to casein plastics, but as a rule, the water absorption is still much too high. Compounding ammoniacal shellac and casein in the presence of potassium stearate and precipitating them with alum, a resin is obtained which can be moulded between 110-120° with good gloss and satisfactory water-resistance.

NITROCELLULOSE AND CELLULOSE ACETATE.

The raw material for the production of nitrocellulose for plastics is generally purified cotton linters. This material consists of cellulose

$(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$, with three hydroxyl groups per $C_6H_{10}O_5$ or anhydroglucose unit. Nitrocellulose is a misnomer since the products obtained from cellulose and nitric acid are esters, the correct term being cellulose nitrate. For each anhydroglucose unit there are three nitrate esters possible. Cellulose nitrate containing about 11 % of nitrogen approximating to dinitrate and soluble in alcohol is the grade preferred for plastics manufacture.

The nitration of cellulose is carried out below 35° by treatment with a nitration mixture consisting of 80% solution of sulphuric and nitric acids in 3:1 proportion. The nitration is completed in 20 minutes and the resulting product contains 10.5 to 11.1% nitrogen. The material is precipitated in water. The nitrocellulose is then centrifuged for the removal of water, final traces of which are removed not by drying but by leaching out with methylated spirits. The damp mass is mixed and kneaded with 30% of camphor, dyed or pigmented, and then rolled into sheets. They are then placed in seasoning rooms under controlled conditions of humidity and temperature to remove alcohol and moisture. Warping can be corrected by pressing the blocks between polished steel platens; 80% of pyroxylin plastics produced are in the form of sheets, about 15% is marketed as rods and 5% as tubes. It is estimated that there are over 25,000 uses for celluloid. It can be produced in an infinite variety of colours and patterns. Celluloid is among the toughest and strongest plastics known and was first prepared in 1868 by John W. Hyatt.

CELLULOSE ACETATE.

For a long time there had been a search by chemists for non-inflammable celluloid. Schutzenberger first acetylated cellulose in 1861. Cellulose acetate, freshly prepared, is unstable and decomposes rapidly in the presence of water. In 1905, G. W. Miles discovered that by ripening the ester at 30° a definite improvement in physical properties takes place.

Cotton linters are added to a mixture of acetic acid, acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid and the temperature is maintained below 20° . In 2 to 6 hours a thick syrup will result, from which the acetate is precipitated by dilution with water, benzene or petroleum ether. This is maintained at 30° for 5 or 6 days and then filtered and dried. Butyl lactate, butyl phthalate, phenol phthalate and phenol lactate are some of the plasticisers used; 10-30% plasticiser are added and further processing is the same as for celluloid.

Ethyl cellulose and benzylcellulose, prepared by treating alkali cellulose with ethyl or benzyl chloride, are recent products that are finding increasing applications.

An important use of celluloid and cellulose acetate is in the manufacture of photographic and cinematographic films.

LIGNIN.

The chief constituents of wood are cellulose and lignin, 20-30% of lignin usually being present. The cellulose unit, since it has not a benzenoid structure, may be considered as aliphatic, whereas lignin is definitely aromatic in structure. Lignin is a compound of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen, but is not a carbohydrate. As would be expected, therefore, lignin has properties very different from cellulose. The lignin unit has been found to contain reactive groups which are capable of resinification with either phenols or aldehydes when heated, preferably in the presence of a catalyst.

Various methods have been proposed for the production of resinous products from lignin. Wood flour or saw dust is commonly used as the raw material, the lignin complex being resinified, the cellulosic component being substantially unchanged and remaining as filler. For example, wood flour and about a quarter of its weight of phenol plus a little hydrochloric acid or ammonia may be heated together, dried and pulverised to give a thernosetting composition which would contain about 50 % of cellulosic material as filler. The product obtained is dark coloured and can be hot pressed. Similar products are claimed to be produced when furfural is used in place of phenol. The bulk of the commercial development of the manufacture of lignin moulding compositions is being carried out in U.S.A.

RUBBER PLASTICS.

Plastic materials for electrical insulation may be obtained from rubber and formaldehyde, or rubber, formaldehyde and phenol. Such bodies have certain properties of both hard rubber and phenol resin. For the preparation of the moulding material, crepe rubber or latex can be used. A typical composition is prepared as follows :—15 kg. of pale crepe rubber are dissolved in 300 kg. of carbon tetrachloride, 25 kg. of sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.14) being stirred in to serve as a condensing agent. 40 Kg. of 40% formaldehyde solution are added, and the mixture is refluxed for 2-3 hours at 100°. The resulting greyish white product, containing free acid, formaldehyde and carbon tetrachloride, is treated with 100 kg. of water and carbon tetrachloride distilled off, about 90% being recovered. The mass is washed with running water until free from acid, dried and milled in a cold mill.

Then it is heated at 95° until dry. The brownish black powder, which is obtained finally, can be moulded at 140°-160° under a pressure of 3000-4000 pounds per sq. inch. It has a specific gravity of 1.95 at 11°, softens at 130°, has a transverse tensile strength of about 400 pounds per square inch and is almost insoluble in all acids, bases, and organic solvents. The moulded articles take a high polish and may be machined, turned, sawed or drilled.

FILLERS.

The various resins described above are not generally used alone for moulding, but they are incorporated with some more or less inert materials, called fillers, the resin functioning as a cementing or binding material. The proper selection and preparation of fillers have pronounced influence on the properties, cost and performance of the finished articles. In general, the addition of fillers to synthetic and natural resins reinforces them and modifies their relatively brittle nature and heat resistance. A satisfactory filler must be cheap and plentiful. Its constancy in composition, *i. e.* freedom from adulterants, impurities, dirt, conducting particles, and excessive moisture, must be invariably secured, and it must be inert and capable of being 'taken up' by the resin with which it is used. It must not also evolve gases under moulding conditions or subsequently.

Mouldings intended to resist high temperatures must be filled with inorganic materials, such as asbestos, mica, chinaclay, magnesia, etc. Mouldings intended for operation at moderate temperatures are usually filled with wood flour. This is the most useful filler and it is cheap and plentiful. The mechanical strength of mouldings designed to stand moderate temperatures is increased by the introduction of a proportion of vegetable fibres such as cotton flock.

The fillers commonly used in moulding compositions may be classified under two divisions: (1) Vegetable—Wood, cotton, hemp, flax, jute; and (2) Mineral—Asbestos, magnesia, chinaclay, mica, slate dust, marble, gypsum, lithopone, titanium oxide, zinc oxide etc. *Wood flour* is one of the most widely used fillers. The most suitable woods are varieties of pine and spruce, not too rich in rosin or oil. In the manufacture of wood flour, the wood fibres are disintegrated either mechanically or chemically, care being taken not to destroy the smallest fibre units by excessive disintegration. As a rule, therefore, wood is ground, or treated under pressure and heat with alkali to obtain the requisite fineness. Generally, 80-100 mesh powder would suffice to give the necessary strength

to the moulded articles. A highly fluffy powder is unsuitable as the bulk of the moulding powder must be low in order to obviate the use of larger moulds which are difficult to make and are also costly.

PREPARATION OF MOULDING POWDERS.

The most widely used procedure for mixing the thermoplastic and particularly the thermosetting moulding composition is the 'dry method' which eliminates the need for solvents and their subsequent removal and recovery. When large amounts of liquid or plastic binders of low softening point are used, the dry process gives a uniform product. This method consists essentially in pulverising the resinous binder and grinding this with other ingredients, lubricant, flux, hardening agent and dyes. The work may be done in a hammer mill or ball mill. The fibrous fillers such as wood flour, cotton flock, asbestos etc. are then added and the blending continued until a uniform mixture is obtained. The light, fluffy powder, prepared in this manner, may be given additional treatment by passing between heated steel cylinders revolving towards each other at slightly different speeds. These are so arranged that the distance between the rolls may be varied during operation at the will of the operator to process the material properly and obtain a sheet of desired thickness. The sheeted material or the blankets are removed from the rollers, cooled and powdered in disintegrators and stored. The loose powders are tableted prior to moulding to reduce bulk and avoid entrapped air, and sometimes preheated to save time in the press or to remove traces of moisture.

SHELLAC.

Shellac is one of the oldest plastics known to civilisation. The fusibility and accurate seal reproduction of sealing waxes were known in Europe during the middle ages. A shellac-moulded casket with elaborate engravings was produced in Birmingham in 1876. As an improvement over rubber mouldings as regards surface finish and speed of output, shellac mouldings came to be adopted for moulded electrical parts. The real impetus for shellac plastics came with the manufacture of gramophone records about the year 1900, in which field it is still supreme, despite hundreds of synthetic resins that have tried to replace it. The present-day synthetic resin plastics industry owes its existence indirectly to shellac, because it was the high price of shellac at Rs. 200 a maund in 1905 that led to the search for synthetic shellac, failure to attain which incidentally resulted in the discovery of commercially practicable synthetic resins. As already stated, the success

attained by Bakelite in 1912 has led chemists all over the world to make fresh discoveries in this ever-widening field of new resins.

India has practically a monopoly of lac production being responsible for about 90%, the rest being grown in Burma, Thailand and Indo-China. The average of the last 10 years' production is nearly 30,000 tons per annum, out of which at a modest estimate, about 10,000 tons are used in the plastics industry every year. The major part of the consumption in the plastics field goes into the production of about 200 million pieces of gramophone records annually, and a small fraction is used in the manufacture of laminated paper and mica articles, grinding wheels, and small dials, knobs and discs for electrical and radio industries.

If shellac compositions are to be more widely used for plastic moulding, they should be capable of being produced at a faster rate than by the hot and cold process and should be much more heat and water resistant than the gramophone record compositions. Recent investigations at the Indian Lac Research Institute have shown that shellac modified by formaldehyde, urea (British Plastics, April, 1939), melamine (*Indian Lac Res. Inst. Res. Note No. 22*), etc. could be worked on the hot moulding technique and shellac modified with formaldehyde and guanidine carbonate filled with jute waste could be injection moulded. The heat resistance of the modified shellac moulded articles is about 90°, and is, therefore, suitable for most purposes. By gradual after-baking, the resistance could, however, be raised to 120° and more.

The theory underlying the modification of shellac by formaldehyde is as yet obscure, but there is sufficient evidence from experimental data that the interaction of shellac with formaldehyde gives rise to a shellac formal :

On heating shellac with formalin for 1—1½ hours, subsequent washing of the product with several changes of hot water, a formal derivative containing 4-6% formaldehyde is obtained which liberates formaldehyde on keeping only slowly. This formal is more plastic than that of shellac itself, and has a softening point of 68°, about 10° lower than shellac. The chief distinguishing characteristic of the formal is its slower polymerisability *i.e.*, longer life under heat. With urea, sufficient heat resistance is developed without giving rise to brittleness even at higher temperatures and longer 'curing time.' The interaction

of urea with the shellac-formal does not, however, completely convert it into a perfectly thermo-hardening material, but urea confers to the formal sufficient thermosetting characteristics to impart to filler-filled moulding powders adequate toughness to enable ejection of moulded articles at temperatures between 140° and 150° without having to take recourse to cooling. The mechanism of the action of urea on the formal may be expressed as below :

This would show that resin formation under these conditions is a quasi-synthetic process, and whilst the totality of the reaction between shellac, formaldehyde and urea produces eventually a resin lying in the borderland of thermosetting and thermoplastic ones, its superior electrical properties, good impact resistance of moulded articles (as high as 8'icm/kg/cm²), and cheapness would speak for the feasibility of this resin being commercially used in the plastics industry. The essence of the reaction with urea is indeed to build up high molecular polymers with the shellac formal, and probably the inability to build still higher polymers is the reason for inferior thermo-hardening properties of this quasi-synthetic resin. Further researches are expected to overcome this difficulty, but the borderland property of the resin enables rejected moulded articles to be recrushed and reused for further moulding. This by itself is of no small advantage, as synthetic thermo-hardening resins do not lend themselves to such operations.

The introduction of a formal grouping in shellac has a most important bearing on the chemical reactivity of the rather inert shellac molecule. In fact, this formal formation has made it possible to bring about condensation of shellac with phenols, the resulting resin having certain good characteristics both for varnishing and plastic moulding purposes. The interaction of 5-10% of phenol with shellac-formal improves the flow of the final resin, but it is still not thermosetting in the sense that bakelite is. The mechanism of the reaction of phenol with shellac-formal is under investigation, but that the condensation is

of a type different from that of bakelite formation is concluded from the fact that the action of urea is necessary for the formation of a suitable resin. The properties of the mechanical mixtures of shellac and bakelite in varying proportions were studied by Ranganathan and Murty (*private communication*.) These are different from the resin now produced by condensation of phenol with shellac formal. The phenomenon of co-polymerisation might be responsible for the improved properties noticed in the latter case.

Mention must be made here of the effect of melamine on the polymerisation of shellac-formals. This chemical, which is assuming importance of late, can substitute urea, and the function of the amino group in the resin formation becomes clearer, as quantities of urea and melamine used to produce the same effect are proportional to the amino groups present in them.

Resins have been prepared at the Indian Lac Research Institute with shellac-formal and melamine,

which are transparent and more thermo-hardening than those with urea and shellac-formals, but they have the disadvantage as yet of being somewhat brittle. Excellent baking varnishes are, however, produced from the shellac-formal-melamine resin with the addition of small quantities of plasticisers. A typical modified shellac moulding powder is prepared as follows :-

The proportions of the different materials employed are :

*Lac	50 lb.
Formalin (35-40%)	25 "
Urea	7.5 "
Calcium stearate	1.25 "
Pigment (brown, black or red)	2.5 "
Wood flour	50.0 "
Rectified spirit	20 gallons

The above materials are digested in a steam-jacketed still, by using steam at 10 lbs. pressure in the jacket for 4 hours, the alcohol

* Either shellac or lac obtained by extracting kiri with alcohol may be used.

being distilled and recovered through a water-cooled condenser as the reaction proceeds. Towards the end of distillation, vacuum is employed to effect a more complete recovery of the alcohol. The pasty mass in the still is taken out and kneaded in a mixing machine of the 'Universal' type under vacuum, the alcohol vapours being condensed and collected. The dried lumps are powdered to 60 mesh in a Christy and Norris disintegrator. The powder is finally dried in vacuum oven at 70° for 2 hours until the batch sample shows non-blistering and free flowing properties when moulded at 140-150° and for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 3 minutes in the press. The powder is then stored in air-tight containers. The cost of manufacture of such a powder works out to be about 4½ annas a pound using good quality shellac. If instead of shellac, lac recovered from *kiri* is used, the cost is reduced to 3½ annas per lb. of moulding powder.

The 'wet process' described above for the manufacture of the moulding powder can be replaced by the 'dry process' recently investigated (*Indian Lac Research Institute Res. Note No. 25*). A considerable saving in the cost of equipment etc. is effected thereby.

From such moulding powders, electro-technical goods like switches, ceiling roses, wall plugs, junction boxes, etc. and general utility articles like soap and powder boxes, cigarette cases, buttons, boards, table-tops, pen and inkstands, etc. could be prepared. If, instead of using a fibrous filler, the resin varnish is applied to paper, mica or textile surfaces and several folds of them are compressed under the hydraulic press, very satisfactory and well polished laminated boards can be produced of diverse utility.

VARIATIONS OF UREA AND FORMALDEHYDE.

In the following experiments 200 g. of shellac and a similar quantity of wood flour were used and the powders dried for one hour at 90° but the quantities of urea and formaldehyde used were varied. The following results were obtained.

Wt. of urea.	Formalin (40% HCHO)	Impact strength (Cm. kg./sq. cm.)	Heat stability (Marten's)
12 g.	37.0 c. c.	5.3	74"
18	56.0	5.45	74
24	75.0	5.9	72
30	94.0	6.0	80
40	125.0	5.6	75
50	150.0	5.8	76

It would appear from the above that the optimum proportion is 15% urea on the weight of lac or, assuming the mol. wt. of lac to be 1000, the following molecular proportions give the best results.

Lac	1 mol.
Urea	2.5 "
Formaldehyde	6.25 "

EFFECT OF VARYING THE AMOUNT OF FORMALDEHYDE.

It is apparent that 15% urea help to increase the heat-resistance but practical experiments show that urea lowers the plasticity, whilst formaldehyde works in the opposite direction. By using 15% urea on the weight of shellac and decreasing the proportion of formaldehyde, the following results were obtained.

No.	Formalin.	Impact strength (Cm. kg./sq. cm.)	Heat stability (Marten's).
1	94 c. c.	6.0	80°
2	47	6.0	79°
3	23.5	4.1	90°

Although it would seem from the above that by using only half the amount of formaldehyde the mechanical and thermal properties were not seriously affected, it was practically noted that powders 2 and 3 had extremely poor flow and produced articles without gloss and uniformity of surface appearance.

EXPERIMENTS WITH DIFFERENT FILLERS.

It is well known that moulded articles of widely differing mechanical and thermal properties can be prepared by variations in the nature and amount of fillers. The following results illustrate the range obtainable with a few selected fillers.

Organic fillers.

Type.	Filler. Percentage	Impact strength (Cm. kg./sq. cm.)	Heat stability (Marten's).
Wood flour	50	6.0	80°
Jute fibre	"	5.6	78
Cotton flock	"	8.8	81
Paper pulp	"	5.2	72

Mineral fillers.

Type	Filler Percentage	Impact strength (Cm. kg./sq. cm.,	Heat stability (Marten's)	Water absorption% 24 hours.
Slate dust	70	2'8	82°	0'09
Asbestos (fine)	"	2'2	88°	0'09
" (fibrous)	"	3'4	90	0'09
Kaolin	"	4'3	80	0'11
Barytes	"	3'4	73	0'09

Among the fillers, cotton flock and asbestos (short fibres) appear to be the most useful. Wood-flour compositions have a moisture absorption of about 0'6 to 1'3% in 24 hours and other cellulosic fillers may be expected to have similar moisture absorption. Where the design of a particular article does not call for a high degree of strength, asbestos-filled articles would be preferable for better gloss, low moisture absorption and higher heat resistance.

SHELLAC-COALTAR AND SHELLAC-CASEIN MOULDING COMPOSITIONS.

Experiments have also been conducted with a view to finding cheaper materials which can replace either partly or wholly urea and formaldehyde used in the previous composition, thereby considerably reducing still the cost of the moulding powder. Shellac and coal-tar (*Indian Lac Research Inst., Res. Note, No. 23*), or its fractions and shellac and casein (*ibid.*, No. 21) have been combined with suitable accelerators and plasticisers to obtain compositions suitable for compression moulding. The articles made with shellac-coal tar compositions are black in colour and with shellac-casein any desirable colour can be obtained.

Besides casein, vegetable proteins obtained from Soyabean, Karanj cakes, etc. have also been successfully incorporated with shellac to obtain cheap moulding compositions suitable for preparing floor tiles, boards, etc.

INJECTION MOULDING.

Apart from the development of shellac moulding powders suitable for compression moulding described above, several other moulding compositions have been investigated for producing articles by the injection moulding process. The principle of injection moulding is, that the composition is fused in a heated barrel and the fused mass is squirted under pressure into a cold closed mould. The chief advantages of injection moulding over compression moulding are, (1) quicker output, (2) less wear on the moulds and (3) the possibility of more intricate mouldings. Among the synthetic resins that have attained commercial success are, cellulose acetate, styrol

compounds, acrylic acid resins, benzyl cellulose, etc. These resins are sold at Rs. 1/8/- to Rs. 3 per pound compared with thermo-hardening moulding powders selling at 8 to 12 annas per pound (pre-war rate).

A typical injection moulding composition from shellac recently developed at the Indian Lac Research Institute is described below :

Shellac (300 parts), jute (cut into short fibres, 200 parts), pigment (100 parts) and calcium stearate (9 parts) are mixed together and ground in a Christy and Norris disintegrator through a 20-25 mesh sieve. The powder, so obtained, is well kneaded with a solution containing formalin (100 parts), guanidin carbonate (15 parts) and water (500 parts). The well-kneaded mass is allowed to stand wet overnight and is then run between hot rollers where it dries and is obtained in the form of large sheets. These are allowed to cool, crushed to a coarse powder (5 to 10 mesh) and is directly used in the injection moulding press. The powder may be worked at a temperature of 125 to 135°. The heat resistance of articles, prepared by the process, is of the order of 70-80°. and the impact resistance is satisfactory.

Several kinds of articles like electrical switches, tumblers, bottle caps, buttons, etc. have been prepared at the Indian Lac Research Institute by injection moulding. These have been well received by the market. The high rate of production of injection moulded articles together with their lower costs is a distinct economic feature. For example, in a single impression switch mould, the rate of production was actually found to be as high as 215 pieces per hour.

RESINS FROM OIL.

The use of vegetable and fish oils, particularly the drying oils for varnishing purpose, is well known and researches on the improvement in the processes are being continually undertaken all over the world. Their use, however, as a plastic resin is of recent origin. A most striking effort in this direction is that of Dr. Goswami at the University College of Science, Calcutta, who has been able to convert all oils in succession into waxy and resinous products by the help of sulphurous and metallic oxides as catalysts under autoclave pressure. No details of the process are as yet known, but from a meagre statement appearing in magazines it is found that the waxes soften between 60° and 90° and that the resins at 100-130°. The resins are thermoplastic but treatment with a little alum followed by vacuum heating makes them thermo-hardening. Thus modified, they can be moulded with 50% wood flour at 200°. The yield of the resin is quantitative and all kinds of oils and fats, vegetable, animal and marine, can be used. The

discoverer proposes the name 'Toilaj' for the plastic, and has already taken out English and Indian Patents.

It is claimed that moulding powders could be produced from this oil resin at 1 to 1½ annas per pound. If the claims can be commercially tested, the process can be considered as a new start in the field of natural or quasi-synthetic plastics.

Whilst the valuable properties of oil resins have made them indispensable in the arts and industries, their use as plastics in combination with shellac has been engaging the attention of workers at the Indian Lac Research Institute. A very interesting observation has been made by Sivaramakrishnan and Venugopalan that when cashewnut shell oil is compounded with shellac (with which it is compatible) resins of varying hardness are obtained according to the proportions of the ingredients used. The films obtained with such compositions are extremely water-resistant and elastic. Modification of such compounded resins with formaldehyde, furfural, acetaldehyde, urea, etc. show excellent promise for supplying a basic resin for the plastic and varnish industries. The presence of the phenolic group in the cashew oil offers greater flexibility in condensation reactions, and the cheap availability of this raw material is expected to exercise an important influence in the natural plastic industry.

MODIFICATION OF SHELLAC WITH FORMALDEHYDE, FURFURALDEHYDE AND ANILINE.

Improved shellac compositions of low acidity for preparing varnishes and polishes of heat and water resistant type are obtained by condensing shellac with suitable proportions of aniline in presence of solvents like acetone, methyl ethyl ketone, etc. A typical composition is prepared as follows :—

100 Grams lac (shellac) are refluxed with 25 c.c. of formalin (40%) over an oil-bath at 120° for 1 hour. The resin formed is then dissolved in 150 c.c. of acetone and 18 c.c. of aniline are gradually added. The whole is then refluxed over a water-bath for 3-4 hours. The resin solution, thus obtained, after dilution with alcohol is used as varnish for coating on metals, wood, etc. Heat and water resistance of the films can be considerably improved by baking at 100-120° for about half an hour.

The resin solution, obtained above, when mixed with suitable plasticisers and fillers like wood flour, jute, asbestos, etc. gives very good thermoplastic moulding compositions which can be used for injection moulding.
